

Portage Progress Report

For the period of January 2017 - March 2017

The following progress report summarizes Portage activities and accomplishments in the first quarter of 2017 corresponding to the goals outlined in the *Portage Business Plan: 2017 - 2018* and provides an update on Portage operations and communications undertaken in this period.

Reporting areas include work undertaken towards:

1. Fostering a community of practice for research data management (RDM);
2. Facilitating and providing leadership in the development of RDM infrastructure;
3. Engaging and advocating for RDM with stakeholder communities; and
4. Developing Portage operations and communications.

Portage's mission is to contribute actively to RDM in Canada through a sustainable network of library-based services and collaborative infrastructure. The following report aims to communicate our progress towards the development of this envisioned national community of practice.

Report prepared by:

Chuck Humphrey (Director, Portage)

Shahira Khair (Training Officer, Portage)

Julie Morin (Project Officer, CARL)

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1. Fostering a community of practice for RDM

A primary objective of Portage is to build a network of expertise for RDM. Critical aspects of this objective are to coordinate and expand on expertise and services within Canadian academic libraries and to build capacity in specific areas of RDM.

Activities and Accomplishments

The following update is centered around the work of the Portage Network of Experts.

Curation Expert Group (CEG):

- Members of the CEG have worked with the Federated Research Data Repository (FRDR) team in the first round of alpha testing of their curation workflow and will continue to play a role in the remaining development stages.
- The CEG has made progress on the completion of their forthcoming white paper, which will provide an environmental scan on the current Canadian context around research data curation platforms, as well as a needs assessment.

Data Discovery Expert Group (DEG):

- The DEG has been overseeing the activity of its recently formed working groups, the Collections Development Working Group and the Metadata Working Group, both of which are half-way through their 6 month mandates.
- The Collections Development Working Group has been identifying the criteria through which repositories will be selected for inclusion in the FRDR search index. To date, they have developed working definitions for “research data” and “repositories” to guide the selection process for repositories to include in FRDR.
- The Metadata Working Group has been evaluating a variety of metadata standards for research data to be included and made discoverable through the FRDR search engine. This has included the development of a metadata crosswalk between standards. They have also been assisting the FRDR development team define core metadata elements for a FRDR Discovery Profile.

Data Management Plan Expert Group (DMPEG):

- The DMPEG has updated its guidance material providing instruction on how to manage research data and use the DMP Assistant. This content has been incorporated on the Portage website.
- The help section for the DMP Assistant is in revision by the group, and they are also in the final stages of approving a revised statement on Privacy and Terms of Use that apply to DMP Assistant.
- DMP Assistant has been enhanced to encrypt the content entered by users. This new functionality is part of the privacy procedures being adopted.
- During this time period, the DMPEG, which is the longest serving expert group, reached the end of its two year mandate to provide tools that support best practices in research data stewardship and to promote a strong data culture in Canada. The group's initial terms of reference ran from March 2015 through February 2017. They are currently in the process of renewing their membership and mandate.

Preservation Expert Group (PEG):

- The PEG is preparing a white paper on the current requirements for research data preservation in Canada, including a description of topics of importance to preservation, such as federated archival storage, and making recommendations that will direct Portage activities in this area.

Research Intelligence Expert Group (RIEG):

- The RIEG has finalized the design of the clearinghouse for the RDM Survey Consortium, to be located on the Portage website. This web resource will contain copies of the RDM Survey questionnaires and ethics applications in both official languages, as well as data deposited by participant institutions.
- The group has also been engaged in developing a roadmap that identifies gaps in our knowledge of RDM practices, developments, culture, and policies in Canada. Once gaps have been discovered, a series of independent studies will be conducted to address them. To this end, RIEG has begun meeting with the other Expert Groups to review the individual environmental scans that have shaped their own work.

Training Expert Group (TEG):

- The TEG has published a white paper entitled *Research Data Management Training Landscape in Canada*, providing a high-level perspective on RDM training in Canada. The group answered some fundamental questions centered on existing expertise and capacity and responded with suggestions for Portage to build RDM expertise and capacity.
- Training materials identified in the process of developing the group's white paper have been compiled and organized for presentation on the Portage website employing a faceted search interface. This resource is seen to address some of the current needs of communities of practice until TEG has developed specific training resources.
- TEG has recently established two working groups that will develop open online training modules focused on: 1) An introduction to RDM; and 2) A guide to completing data management plans.
- TEG has also been engaged in completing an online request form for on-demand training on various subjects of RDM.

2. Facilitating and providing leadership in the development of RDM infrastructure

Portage seeks to advance the development of national platforms for planning, curating, preserving and discovering research data. This will require working with infrastructure providers – both in the library community and elsewhere – to develop new tools where gaps exist and to bridge systems where interoperability is needed.

Activities and Accomplishments

DMP Assistant

- A revised Privacy Statement and Terms of Use applied to DMP Assistant are in the final stages of implementation by DMPEG.
- An upgrade to the DMP Assistant has been implemented to encrypt the text entered by users, which forms part of the revised privacy procedures being adopted.
- Weiwei Shi, lead developer for DMP Assistant, participated in a collaborative software development meeting with the team producing a unified codebase for DMP Online and DMP Tool in Edinburgh, Scotland from February 16-17, 2017. A new release of DMP Assistant based on this new codebase is planned for the Fall of 2017.

Federated Research Data Repository (FRDR)

- The alpha phase of the FRDR project concluded at the end of March 2017 and involved the evaluation and adjustment of the user interfaces for submitting, curating, and searching databases. A detailed outline of the objectives completed is available for review as part of a project update maintained jointly by the Canadian Association of Research Libraries (CARL) and Compute Canada (available at www.computecanada.ca/rdm).
- A prototype of the interface and underlying software are ready for the beta testing phase, set to begin in April 2017. In preparation, a logo for FRDR has been finalized, as was the layout and text for the public interface. A brochure site was also created by Portage to promote FRDR and the release of the beta test site.

- Institutional development has advanced at both CARL and Compute Canada in preparation for the platform and services that will be needed during the pilot (set for Fall 2017) and production (set for early 2018) phases.

Dataverse North

- The Dataverse North Working Group was formed by Portage in conjunction with the Canadian institutions hosting local Dataverse instances (OCUL Scholars Portal, UBC Libraries, and University of Alberta Libraries).
- The group will work to develop a community of practice for libraries using or interested in using the Dataverse repository platform for research data in Canada. They will also investigate gaps and opportunities that could be addressed by nationally coordinated strategies and services for Dataverse, including training, infrastructure development, and support for researchers and librarians, including hosting services provided by regional Dataverse providers.
- A Call for Participation in the working group was released March 23, 2017 and has received an enthusiastic, Canada-wide response.

PREFER: A Format Policy Register

- Scholars Portal, in collaboration with Portage and COPPUL, submitted an EOI to CANARIE for funding to develop a format policy register for research data. This web service would permit machine-to-machine inquiries about formats preferred for the preservation and dissemination of research data. This project was not among those invited to submit a full proposal.
- Martha Whitehead, Susan Haigh, and Chuck Humphrey met with Jim Ghadbane, President of CANARIE, and Mark Leggott, Executive Director of RDC, on March 16, 2017 to discuss possible collaborations between Portage and CANARIE. Jim advised working directly with Mark to develop a format policy register. Other web services supportive of research data management were discussed, including secure data enclave services, assessment of disclosure risk for confidential data, and anonymization services for confidential data.

3. Engaging and advocating for RDM with stakeholder communities

The task of managing data from research across Canada requires community-wide involvement and collaboration. The major components of the Network are based on a thorough understanding of researchers' needs and on solid working relationships with funding agencies, data stewards, infrastructure providers, regional academic library consortia and international collaborators.

Activities and Accomplishments

Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada (SSHRC) DMP Workshop

- A successful capstone event, held January 24 2017, completed Portage's engagement with the SSHRC DMP Workshop. The recipients of eighteen SSHRC Insight and Partnership grants from a range of disciplines in the humanities and social sciences participated in this Workshop, which began in October 2016. Participants were asked to complete a DMP for their research projects using DMP Assistant. The name of a local library contact who could assist with preparing the DMP was provided to the researchers. Once a DMP was submitted, researchers were asked to complete an online questionnaire about their experience. The in-person capstone event was attended by 17 researchers and data managers from 13 research projects. In addition, 18 observers from RDM stakeholder organizations joined the researchers to discuss the opportunities and challenges of participating in the Workshop.
- A final report summarizing the Workshop and lessons learned has been submitted to SSHRC and is slated for public release.

Outreach to the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC)

- Chuck Humphrey (Director, Portage) and Dugan O'Neil (Chief Scientist, Compute Canada) were invited to speak on January 27, 2017 at an NSERC session about the partnership between their two organizations in developing FRDR and about the next phase of Portage service development to support data repository and discovery platforms.

RDM modules for the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR)

- The contract to develop the content for a series of six online RDM training modules for the CIHR website concluded in March 2017. Three members of TEG were joined by three volunteers from the academic library community to form the writing team for this project.

Members submitted finalized drafts of content for the modules, as well as accompanying case studies and FAQ's. CIHR is set to make the modules publicly available in the Fall of 2017.

Canadian Space Agency (CSA) Life Science Contract

- Portage's contribution to the CSA Life Sciences investigation into the archiving of research data from CSA-funded projects concluded in March 2017. The contractors made an in person presentation on the final report at CSA on February 3, 2017. Some additional questions were raised following this presentation that were addressed and accepted in March 2017. The Portage Director worked with Janet Halliwell, who was the primary contractor for this project. CARL received payment for the Director's time to conduct background research, to interview CSA-funded researchers and relevant stakeholders, such as members of the NASA data repository for life sciences, and to contribute to the writing of the report. The authors encouraged CSA to make the final report publicly available because of its applicability to other government funding agencies and the wider RDM community.

Canadian RDM Survey Consortium

- McMaster University, Western University, and the University of Victoria joined the RDM survey consortium in the first quarter of 2017, bringing the total to 14 institutions to conduct surveys of their researchers.
- Final survey datasets are being collected for public release through a clearinghouse hosted on the Portage website, which is currently in development by RIEG.

Presentations by the Portage Director to CARL Institutions

- On January 25 2017, Carleton University Library hosted a half-day campus forum on RDM. Wayne Jones (University Librarian, Carleton University) introduced the program and Chuck Humphrey gave one of several presentations for the day on the subject of RDM and the ongoing work of Portage. Jeff Moon, Chair of DMPEG, also spoke, describing the data rescue service implemented at Queen's Library.
- On January 26 2017, the University of Ottawa Library hosted two RDM events. A public session included an introduction by Leslie Weir (University Librarian, University of Ottawa) about the library's engagement in RDM. Chuck Humphrey spoke about issues in RDM and how the library community in Canada is supporting the research community in this area. A

private session was held with uOttawa librarians and invited campus colleagues to discuss local support for research data. Chuck Humphrey spoke about how the Portage Network of Expertise and platforms for research data infrastructure can support librarians in their local context. As well, Jeff Moon made a presentation about Queen's research data management services.

- On February 15, 2017, McGill University Library hosted Chuck Humphrey as an invited speaker at private events for librarians and research administrators. At a morning session, the Director spoke to subject and liaison librarians on subjects concerning RDM, while at an afternoon session, the Director participated in a roundtable discussion between librarians and program officers from the McGill Office of Sponsored Research.

Leadership Council for Digital Infrastructure (LCDI)

- Innovation, Science, and Economic Development (ISED) has funded LCDI to provide recommendations to this Federal department about national directions for digital research infrastructure (DRI). Robbin Tourangeau (Executive Director, LCDI) has organized working groups to assist in preparing this report. Martha Whitehead (President, CARL), Susan Haigh (Executive Director, CARL), Chuck Humphrey (Director, Portage), Mark Leggott (Executive Director, RDC), and David Baker (Executive Director, CASRAI) were invited by Robbin to participate on the LCDI research data management working group. This group met on January 6, 2017, February 16, 2017, and March 17, 2016 to define key concepts and to provide a functional description of research data management that policy makers need to understand when funding this area of digital research infrastructure. Between meetings of this working group, Chantel Ridsdale (LCDI Secretariat) and Chuck Humphrey provided more detailed background based on the discussions of the in person meetings.
- Representing two of the five functional components of the LCDI digital research infrastructure model, the RDM and Advanced Research Computing working groups met in a joint session on the morning of February 28, 2017 to discuss common terminology, definitions, and approaches to describing their DRI functions. In the afternoon, both working groups attended a membership meeting of the LCDI and contributed to a progress report on the work being prepared for ISED.

4. Developing Portage operations and communications

Portage is a CARL initiative and is currently supported through its membership. The goal is to develop a sustainable network built upon the support of the wider research data management ecosystem.

Undertakings and Accomplishments

Governance

- It is anticipated that as the network develops over the next several years, the governance structure will evolve. In January 2017 the newly implemented governance structure formed in 2016 was revised slightly for 2017 and 2018, as per the diagram below. The change is the addition of a CARL Directors Portage Steering Committee to reflect the continuing financial commitments of CARL institutions during this period.

The CARL Directors Portage Steering Committee

- The CARL Directors Portage Steering Committee (CDPSC) consist of three to six Directors appointed by the CARL Board to provide additional member input into and oversight of Portage. The Chair of this group will also sit as a member of the Portage Advisory Committee. The CDPSC sets directions and priorities for the operational services of the Network of Expertise and collaborative RDM platforms. The CDPSC recommends to the Board plans for Portage during and beyond this period and supports the Portage Director in preparing Governance and Business models for ongoing operations. Furthermore, it will review and recommend to the Board operating principles, policies, and procedures as well as priorities for investment and areas for development.

First Meeting of the Newly Formed CDPSC

- On March 2, 2017 the members of the CDPSC were formally announced:

March to May 2017

- Martha Whitehead - Chair
(CARL President - voting *ex officio*)
- Larry Alford
- Guylaine Beaudry
- Catherine Steeves
- Brett Waytuck
- Donna Bourne-Tyson
(CARL VP – non-voting *ex officio*)
- Susan Haigh
(CARL ED - non-voting *ex officio*)
- Chuck Humphrey
(Portage Director - non-voting *ex officio*)

June 2017 to March 2019

- Donna-Bourne-Tyson - Chair
(CARL President - voting *ex officio*)
- Larry Alford
- Guylaine Beaudry
- Catherine Steeves
- Brett Waytuck
- Martha Whitehead
- Jonathan Bengtson- To be confirmed
(CARL VP – non-voting *ex officio*)
- Susan Haigh
(CARL ED - non-voting *ex officio*)
- Chuck Humphrey - then his successor
(Portage Director - non-voting *ex officio*)

- The group will be meeting for the first time on April 12, 2017 and will be discussing the implementation of the 2017-2018 Business Plan, including the approval of a Communication Plan, Work Plan, and Formative Assessment..

Portage Advisory Committee

- The Advisory Committee (AC) will offer guidance to the Portage Director and CARL Directors Portage Steering Committee on directions and priorities during the period of the Business Plan, 2017-2018. The AC will also provide advice on the preparation of plans for Portage beyond this period, specifically helping the Portage Director prepare Governance and Business models for ongoing operations. Furthermore, it will review and advise on operating principles, policies, and procedures and will identify priorities for investment and areas for development.

First Meeting of the Newly Formed Portage Advisory Committee

- The AC will meet for the first time under its new mandate on April 25, 2017. Steven Liss, VPR at Ryerson University, has graciously consented to serving as the Chair of the AC. The membership is very similar to the initial Portage Steering Committee in 2016 and brings valuable guidance from key Canadian RDM stakeholders.

Organization	Members	Organization	Members
Bureau de coopération interuniversitaire	Guylaine Beaudry	Leadership Council for Digital Infrastructure	Graham Carr
Canadian Association of Research Administrators	Karina McInnis	Ontario Council of University Libraries	TBC
Canadian Association of Research Ethics Boards	Susan Babcock Rachel Zand	Portage	Chuck Humphrey
Canadian Association of Research Libraries	Donna Bourne-Tyson Susan Haigh Martha Whitehead	Research Data Canada	Mark Leggott
Council of Atlantic University Libraries	James MacKenzie	Ryerson University	Steven Liss (Chair)
Compute Canada	Dugan O'Neil	Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council	Matthew Lucas
Council of Prairie and Pacific University Libraries	Brian Owen	UK Digital Curation Centre	Kevin Ashley
Canadian University Council of Chief Information Officers	Lori McMullen Terry Nikkel Bo Wandschneider	University of Alberta Libraries	Geoff Harder

Implementation of the 2017-2018 Business Plan : Work Plan and Communications Plan

- In early February, work began on a Communications Plan for Portage, outlining the communication objectives, timeframe, channels, activities, and responsibilities. A Work Plan for Portage was also drafted, describing the timeframe, lead responsibility, and staff support for all of the deliverables outlined in the Business Plan. Both of these documents will be reviewed during the first meeting of the Carl Directors Portage Steering Committee.

Internal Assessment Announcement

- Also in accordance with the Portage Business Plan for 2017-2018, a draft of a Formative Assessment Plan was started in March 2017, including a description of objectives, target audiences and methodology, and an evaluation framework outlining research questions, indicators, sources and instruments. The Draft Assessment Plan will be discussed during the first quarterly meeting of the CARL Directors Portage Steering Committee.

New Staff

- Candidates were interviewed in December 2016 for the 0.5FTE position of Training Officer that was approved in the Portage Business Plan. Shahira Khair was offered and accepted this position along with a 0.5FTE appointment with CARL's assessment activities. Shahira has a Masters degree in Biology and is in her final term completing a Masters of Information Studies with the University of Ottawa School of Information Studies. In addition to this Julie Morin was offered and accepted a 0.5FTE position as Project Officer for CARL, and will be providing support with Portage governance activities. Julie graduated from the Masters of Library and Information Studies Program at McGill in 2014. We are excited with the talent and enthusiasm that they bring to Portage and CARL.

Website Structure Updated

- The Portage website, which was made publicly available on April 15, 2016, needed updating to reflect the growth of the Network's operations since the site's launch. For example, the "About Portage" tab contained a disproportionate amount of the website's information in April 2016. As the expert groups became established and started to produce reports and working group projects, new content for the website was generated. It became clear by January 2017 that the original organization of information needed restructuring. Shahira Khair designed a new architecture for the site and implemented this in February 2017. In

particular, she created a tab for “Work with Portage” that moved expert group information from “About Portage” to a more direct location and that now contains more content about the expert groups and their products. With the assistance of the DMP Expert Group, the content for “How to Manage Your Data” was refreshed and expanded. Web space was also provided to the chairs of the expert groups so they can maintain their own updates.